

The Influence of Organizational Culture and Competence on Work Stress Mediated by Workload on Employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province

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ABSTRACT: Organizational Culture that is oriented towards the regularity of observed behavior, strong norms, dominant values, philosophy, rules, and organizational climate directly contributes to the increasing Work Stress felt by employees, in the form of physiological symptoms, psychological symptoms, and behavioral symptoms. Likewise, Competence that is oriented towards high knowledge, understanding, ability, values, attitudes, and interests, but is less in accordance with the competencies needed to carry out the work that is directly responsible contributes to the increasing Work Stress felt by employees, in the form of physiological symptoms, psychological symptoms, and behavioral symptoms.

The research findings show that Organizational Culture and Competence have a significant positive impact on employee Work Stress. Organizational Culture encourages the creation of an obligation to submit to and comply with strict regulations governing the main tasks and functions in carrying out work, but the process of determining the regulations themselves is very long, so that when the regulations are issued, it is close to the deadline for the work implementation stage, this makes it difficult for employees because they have to immediately learn, adjust and adopt the regulations to complete the work with a limited deadline, in the end this condition causes the work stress felt by employees to increase. While the high Competence possessed but not in accordance with the work that is the responsibility causes a lack of sufficient understanding of the character of the work that is the responsibility and knowledge that does not comply with the standards set causes the Work Stress felt by employees to increase, because employees are required to be able to adapt and work in new fields of work that are far different from the competencies they have. In this study, statistically Workload has a significant positive influence as a mediator of the influence of the variables Organizational Culture and Competence on Work Stress. This shows that Workload is able to help explain why Organizational Culture and Competence cause Work Stress felt by employees to increase.

This study underlines the importance of creating a more positive organizational culture, ensuring that each employee has high competencies that are appropriate or suitable for the field of work they are responsible for, and carefully managing the existing workload. These findings provide valuable insights for organizations that seek to manage employee work stress levels by utilizing appropriate regulatory practices, understanding, knowledge, and skills appropriate to the field of work being worked on, and adjustments to work conditions, target setting, and better use of working time.

KEYWORDS: Competence, Organizational Culture, Workload, Work Stress.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern era like today, new technologies continue to emerge and develop rapidly. The role of technology is very much needed in companies to support their operational activities so that they can continue to exist in increasingly fierce competition. As stated by Rahman and Pratama (2022), digital change is currently developing rapidly and affecting almost all areas of life. Digital transformation is the result of the era of disruption or better known as Industry 4.0 which leads to changes in business models that change the current business ecosystem into a new, more innovative ecosystem. In the business world, rapid technological developments require companies to be able to compete in sustainable competition. Research by Jovita, et al., (2024) shows that the use of information technology has brought significant changes in the operational efficiency of companies, through business process automation, sophisticated data analysis, and increased operational visibility. In addition, information technology is also an important catalyst in driving innovation and business growth, by providing easier access to data and information, facilitating closer collaboration between stakeholders, and enabling the adoption of new business models driven by technology. Human resources are the heart of the

company that drives all existing systems in the company. Human resources are important for organizations to have, because the success of an organization is largely determined by the human element (Ardana, 2012). In carrying out their duties accompanied by the ever-growing digital transformation, employees of an agency have pressure that can cause work stress (Anggara, 2019). Employees are the main assets in an organization that must be managed and utilized in a balanced and humane manner so that employees do not experience work stress (Ananda, et al., 2021). According to Robbins & Judge (2017), indicators of work stress include physiological symptoms, psychological symptoms, and behavioral symptoms.

Based on interviews from initial observations conducted by researchers, the problem at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province is damage to the laptop used for work. When the laptop is damaged, it automatically makes employees unable to work optimally. Not only that, there are also tasks that require employees to upload work files to an application. However, because the quality of the WiFi signal in the office of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province is weak, the process of uploading documents takes a long time. This makes employees often worry that if there is a process of uploading documents that takes a long time, the collection of documents will exceed the specified time limit. This condition is also exacerbated by problems with the application used to upload the work. The latest example is that not long ago the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province was given the task of uploading data related to the Voting Organizer Group through an application. However, the application itself experienced problems that made the application inaccessible, making the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province unable to upload data. The existence of these problems delayed work and caused employee work productivity to decrease. In addition, each employee can handle two to three sub-sections of work at once. In the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, usually one section consists of two subsections, in one subsection can get more than one task at the same time. The uncertainty of work related to the many subsections of work that are the responsibility, causes work demands to multiply, thus causing employees to experience work stress. Almost all employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province often complain and feel tired because of the large amount of work that must be completed. This happens because some jobs require employees to move from one location to another, not only having to go to one district or within the scope of the Special Region of Yogyakarta province, but also having to go out of town. In addition to causing employees to often complain and feel tired, it also causes some employees to be late to the office. Lateness of employees in working causes work to be delayed.

Work stress can be influenced by several factors, one of which is organizational culture. Luthans (2011) stated that one indicator of organizational culture is rules. Rules are strict guidelines regarding socializing in an organization. Every employee must learn the "rules" in order to be fully accepted as a member of the group. Based on interviews from initial observations conducted by researchers, at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, regulations related to the stages of the General Election adopted to be determined and implemented must come from regulations issued by the center. The problem is, the process of issuing regulations is very long, so that when the regulations are issued, the deadline for the stages of the General Election is approaching. This condition makes it difficult for the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province because they have to immediately study, adjust and adopt the regulations to carry out the election stages, with a very limited deadline. The existence of this condition increases the work stress felt by employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. Research conducted by Clarisa, et al., (2022), Edwin (2023) and Komar (2021) shows that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on work stress. This is also different from research conducted by Aulia (2021) and Sofiana, et al., (2021) which shows that organizational culture has a negative and insignificant effect on work stress.

Another factor that can affect work stress is competence. According to Tantra & Larasati (2015) competence that is not appropriate and cannot develop with job demands will cause work stress, which will ultimately hinder the company in achieving its goals. One of the indicators of competence according to Gordon (2017) is knowledge, understanding, and ability. Based on interviews from initial observations conducted by researchers, in general all employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province are able to carry out their duties as assigned. However, it cannot be denied that at certain times there are some employees who lack the knowledge, understanding, and ability to complete their work, both in terms of the content of their own tasks and the applications used to support the work. This happens because there have been several organizational changes in the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province which increasingly test the competence of

employees. The purpose of the organizational changes that occur is that at some point each employee can be transferred from one work section to another.

Almost all activities at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province have Standard Operating Procedures that regulate, then socialized to all employees, so that employees understand the existing Standard Operating Procedures. However, there have been several changes in regulations, so that the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province must evaluate and update the existing Standard Operating Procedures, then socialize them again to employees. The solution taken by the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province to train and improve the competence of its employees as a step in responding to conditions that require employees to have high competence is by creating a program called knowledge sharing. However, in practice, this knowledge sharing program cannot be carried out routinely. Research conducted by Maliki, et al., (2024) and Marbella (2020) shows that competence has a positive and significant effect on work stress. This is also different from research conducted by Tungka, et al., (2023), Lestari and Darmo (2022) which shows that competence has a negative and insignificant effect on work stress.

Furthermore, the factor that influences employee work stress is workload. According to Robins & Judge (2017), many professionals view the pressure of heavy workloads and deadlines as positive challenges that drive the quality of their work and the satisfaction they get from their work. However, when the situation becomes negative, stress becomes dangerous and will hinder employee progress. Task demands that cause excessive workload are considered to increase anxiety and stress in employees. However, the difference is shown in the results of previous research conducted by Clarisa, et al., (2022) which found that workload cannot mediate the influence of organizational culture on work stress. Workload indicators according to Koesomowidjojo (2017) include work conditions, use of working time, and targets to be achieved. Based on interviews from the initial observations conducted by the researcher, related to work conditions, although the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province did not implement the Regional Head Election in accordance with the Special Autonomy Law, the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province has a position as a regional coordinator, so that in the stages of the Regional Head Election, the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province is always involved. The General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province also has its own routine tasks. Routine tasks that must be completed by employees can reach several or many tasks at once at one time, so that the workload at that time tends to be heavy. Furthermore, related to the use of working hours and targets that must be achieved, at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province all tasks must and must be completed according to the deadline and targets that have been set without exception. There are tasks that are daily in nature, and some must be completed that day, so they must be completed that day too. Then there are also tasks that are stages that must be completed with a certain time limit that has been set by the center, and usually these tasks can be completed by employees approaching the last seconds of the deadline set. This condition shows that the workload that must be completed is very large because it must use the entire total time given, and can only be fulfilled near the last seconds. In addition, at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province when entering the General Election stage, working hours are until 24 hours, and this is not considered overtime, but exceeds the time limit to go home or exceeds the working time limit of 8 hours. So at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, 8 hours is only for administration, but its implementation can be more than that according to needs. Not only that, on Saturdays and Sundays administratively it should be a holiday or there are no duties, but at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province on Saturdays and Sundays they still often carry out duties. This condition occurs because of the many targets that must be achieved and completed, both related to daily duties and duties for the General Election stages. In addition, there are still some employees who often ask or have to ask for help from other employees, leaders or even the center to explain their work. Because sometimes the understanding between employees regarding the duties and applications used to support work varies. However, research conducted by Clarisa, et al., (2022) shows that workload cannot mediate the influence of organizational culture on work stress.

Research Objectives

This study aims to explore the interaction between Organizational Culture, Competence, and Workload on Employee Work Stress at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. Specifically, this study aims to:

1. Examine the direct impact of Organizational Culture on Work Stress.
2. Assess the influence of Competence on Work Stress.

3. Investigate the mediating role of Workload on the influence of Organizational Culture on Work Stress.
4. Explore the mediating role of Workload on the influence of Competence on Work Stress.

By discussing these objectives, this study can provide information for the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province regarding factors that can affect employee Work Stress, namely Organizational Culture, Competence, and Workload. So that this study can be used as a consideration and input for the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. This study also contributes as a source of in-depth information related to the topics raised in the study, and can provide knowledge and insight in analyzing work stress, organizational culture, competence, and employee workload.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Attribution Theory

According to Fritz Heider (1958), this theory is the first theory that examines the attribution process, especially on how someone builds a compression or impression for others. Messages or impressions are built through three stages of the process, namely observing behavior, determining whether the behavior is intentional or unintentional, and grouping behavior into behavior that is motivated internally or externally. Basically, attribution theory states that when individuals observe someone's behavior, they try to determine whether the behavior is caused internally or externally. Internally caused behavior is behavior that is under the personal control of the individual himself in a conscious state, such as personality traits, awareness, and abilities. While externally caused behavior is behavior that is influenced from outside, meaning that individuals will be forced to behave because of the situation or environment such as the social influence of others.

The first important elements in Attribution Theory are Distinction, referring to whether an individual displays different behavior in different situations. The second is Consensus, if everyone facing the same situation gives the same response, the observer can say that the behavior shows consensus. The last important element in Attribution Theory is Consistency, an observer looks for consistency in a person's actions. Whether or not the person responds the same way over time. The more consistent the behavior, the more likely the leader (observer) is to attribute it to internal causes (Robbins & Judge, 2017).

The Job Demand-Control Model (JDC)

The Job Demand-Control Model (JDC) explains that job stress is an interactive effect between demands and control. This theory has two assumptions, the first is that the combination of high job demands with low job control will produce work that has physical and psychological stress. Second, work with high job demands and job control will produce well-being, learning and personal growth. Thus, based on the Job Demand-Control (JDC) model, job demands and job control are combined interactively to predict work-related outcomes (Karasek, 1979). Karasek and Theorell (1990) expanded the model by including factors that determine individual stress levels, namely social support. Karasek & Theorell (1990) define social support in the workplace as "the overall level of beneficial social interaction available in the workplace from coworkers and supervisors". This model is then known as Job Requirements Management Support (JDMS).

Work Stress

Work stress is a condition of tension that creates physical and psychological imbalances that affect emotions, thought processes and conditions of an employee. The level of job stress arises as a form of disharmony between individuals and the work environment (Robbins & Morelli, 2014). According to Afandi (2018), job stress is a condition that arises due to the interaction between individuals and their work, where there is a mismatch in characteristics and unclear changes that occur in the company.

The Consequences of Work Stress according to Robbins & Judge (2017) are, stress appears in various forms, such as high blood pressure, ulcers, irritability, difficulty making routine decisions, changes in appetite, prone to accidents, and the like. These symptoms are divided into three general categories: physiological, psychological, and behavioral symptoms. Physiological Symptoms, Stress can cause changes in metabolism, increase heart rate and breathing and blood pressure, cause headaches, and cause heart attacks. Almost all employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province often complain and feel tired because of the large amount of work that must be completed. In addition, there are several jobs that require employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province to move from one location to another, not only having to go to one district or within the scope of the Special Region of Yogyakarta province, but also having to go out of town.

Psychological Symptoms, stress appears in other psychological conditions, for example, tension, anxiety, irritability, boredom, and delays. In the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, there is job uncertainty related to the many sub-sections of work that are the responsibility, which causes work demands to multiply, and the high mobility of work, in addition to causing employees to often complain and feel tired, also causes some employees to be late to the office. The delay of employees in working causes work to be delayed.

Behavioral Symptoms, stress related to behavior include decreased productivity, absenteeism, and employee turnover, as well as changes in eating habits, increased smoking or alcohol consumption, rapid speech, restlessness, and sleep disturbances. In the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, there are several employees who are late to the office. The delay from employees causes a decrease in the level of productivity at work.

Organizational Culture

Organizational Culture is a pattern of basic assumptions that are taught to each employee as the correct way to understand, think, and act on a daily basis (Luthans, 2011). Organizational culture refers to a system of shared meanings that are held and owned by members that distinguishes an organization from other organizations (Robbins & Judge, 2017).

Furthermore, Luthans (2011) stated that several important characteristics of Organizational Culture are Observed Behavioral Regularities, when employees in the organization interact with each other, they use the same language, terminology, and rituals related to respect and attitude. Another important characteristic of Organizational Culture is Norms, which are standards of behavior, including guidelines on how much work should be done.

Dominant Values are the third important characteristic of Organizational Culture, which focuses on the main values that the organization supports and expects employees to share.

The next important characteristic of Organizational Culture is Philosophy, which establishes the organization's beliefs about how employees and/or customers should be treated.

Rules are the fifth important characteristic of Organizational Culture, which focuses on strict guidelines regarding socializing in the organization. Every employee must learn the "rules" in order to be fully accepted as a member of the group.

The last important characteristic of Organizational Culture is Organizational Climate, which is the overall feeling conveyed through the physical layout, the way employees in the organization interact, and the way they behave with customers or other outsiders.

Resource Based View (RBV)

RBV was first introduced by Wernerfelt (1984) and further developed by Barney (1991), focusing on the identification, management, and utilization of resources and capabilities owned by the organization. According to this theory, an organization can achieve sustainable competitive advantage if it is able to have resources that meet the criteria of Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, and Non-Substitutable (VRIN). In other words, organizations that can integrate and manage their unique resources effectively have a greater chance of excelling in the market compared to competitors.

The first main characteristic of RBV (VRIN) is Valuable, a resource is said to be valuable if it can help the company achieve operational efficiency and effectiveness, while meeting market needs. Modern technology, such as automated manufacturing systems, can increase productivity, reduce costs, and provide added value to customers. In operational management, the utilization of valuable resources allows companies to better face competitive pressures (Peteraf Barney, 2021).

The second is Rare, the scarcity of resources is one of the factors that makes it strategic. Rare resources create differentiation that is difficult for competitors to imitate. For example, a patent on a particular technological innovation can provide a company with an exclusive competitive advantage. In operations, this scarcity can be realized through exclusive access to high-quality raw materials or unique technology (Teece, 2020).

Inimitable is the third main characteristic of RBV (VRIN), focusing on the complexity, secrecy, or uniqueness of certain resources that make them difficult for competitors to imitate. For example, a strong organizational culture, specific managerial experience, or carefully designed business processes are elements that are difficult to replicate. In the context of operational management, companies that have unique expertise in managing supply chains or advanced manufacturing technologies will be more difficult to match (Priemetal, 2021).

The last main characteristic of RBV (VRIN) is Non-Substitutable, this characteristic refers to resources that have no other alternatives with equivalent value. For example, workers with specialized expertise in a particular technology or a very specific

manufacturing process are difficult to replace by other technologies. Dependence on resources like this gives the company a unique advantage that is not easily matched by competitors (Grant Verona, 2020).

Competence

Competence according to Edison, et al., (2017) is a person's ability to do good and correct work according to knowledge, expertise and attitude. According to Palan (2007) competence is a description of behavior, which in more detail refers to the characteristics underlying behavior that describe motives, personal characteristics (traits), self-concept, values, knowledge or expertise brought by someone who performs superiorly (superior performer) in the workplace.

Competence elements according to Gordon (2017) are Knowledge, which is an individual's awareness in the cognitive field. For example, an employee who works in a company knows how to learn and how to do good learning according to the needs of the company.

The second is Understanding, namely individuals who have cognitive depth. In every learning, they must have a good understanding of the characteristics and working conditions effectively and efficiently.

The third element of competence is Ability, which is something that every individual has in carrying out the tasks and responsibilities assigned.

Value is the fourth element of competence that focuses on behavioral standards that are believed to have been integrated in each individual. For example, employee behavior in carrying out tasks such as honesty, openness, and democracy.

The fifth element of competence is Attitude, which is a feeling such as happy and unhappy, like and dislike or the reaction of each individual to a stimulus that comes from outside. For example, feelings about a salary increase.

Interest is the last element of competence, which focuses on the tendency of each individual to do something. For example, doing a work activity.

Role Theory

Mead (1934) through his symbolic interactionist perspective focuses on the role of individual factors, the evolution of roles through social interaction, and various forms of cognitive concepts with which social actors understand and interpret behavioral guidelines for themselves and others. Meanwhile, Linton (1936) uses a structural approach to explain the behavioral characteristics of a person who occupies a certain social position in an established social system. "Role" is further conceptualized as normative expectations that are firmly held and become the basis for the creation of these behaviors. On the other hand, Moreno's (1934) thinking is based on the relationships between role expectations and behavior, the social conditions that give rise to these expectations, and the ways in which a person perceives other people's expectations and understands their influence on behavior.

Multiple Resource Theory (MRT)

Multiple Resource Theory (MRT) proposed by Wickens (1984) shows that there are many resource pools that reach a threshold when demand exceeds the resource pool. As a result, working memory, for example, can only process a limited amount of information at a given time as proposed by information theory (Shannon & Weaver, 1949). According to Wickens (1984) in Multiple Resource Theory (MRT) performance is seen as a human capacity that has limitations to understand information or can be interpreted as a short-term resource that is different from other resources. In calculating performance, companies can see through several factors, one of which is through the calculation of tasks assigned to employees. Excess workload caused by a task that uses similar resources will cause several problems and errors and slowness in completing the task. This also applies if the task is completed simultaneously with demands on the same part, it will cause excess workload that causes employee fatigue so that it can reduce their performance.

Workload

Workload is a collection or number of activities that must be completed by an organizational unit within a specified time (Koesomowidjojo, 2017). According to Hard and Staveland (2017) workload is something that arises from the interaction between the demands of the work environment tasks where it is used as a workplace.

According to Koesomowidjojo (2017), the elements of workload are: Work Conditions, which is how an employee understands the job well.

The second element of Workload is the Use of Working Time, time in accordance with the Standard Operating Procedure will certainly minimize the workload of employees, but sometimes a company does not have a Standard Operating Procedure or is

inconsistent in implementing the Standard Operating Procedure, the use of working time imposed on employees tends to be excessive or very narrow.

The last element of Workload is the Target to be Achieved, the work target set by the company will of course directly affect the workload received by employees. The narrower the time provided to carry out certain work or the imbalance between the completion time of the target implementation or the volume of work given, the greater the workload received and felt by employees.

Inter-Variable Influence

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Work Stress

According to Manullang (2021), a positive organizational culture can increase employee motivation, engagement, and productivity, reduce stress, fatigue, and burnout. Conversely, a negative organizational culture can cause stress and burnout. A positive organizational culture can lead to increased productivity, decreased stress, and higher employee retention. Yuwono (2014) stated that organizational culture has a negative role in the level of stress of an employee when working in an organization. This is supported by research conducted by Edwin (2023), Clarisa, et al., (2022), and Komar (2021) which found that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on work stress.

H1: Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Work Stress of Employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province.

The Influence of Competence on Work Stress

According to Pradnyani, et al., (2022) competence is one part of the internal causes of someone experiencing work stress or known as dispositional attribution. It can be simply explained that the more competent an employee is, the lower the work stress they experience. Individuals with good competence when placed in appropriate positions tend to experience minimal work stress because they are able to do their jobs well. In addition, individuals with competence that is in accordance with their field of work will be able to manage work and even have their own way of completing their work. According to Tantra and Larasati (2015) competence that is not appropriate and cannot develop with the demands of the job will cause work stress, which will ultimately hinder the company from achieving its goals. This is supported by research conducted by Maliki, et al., (2024) and Marbella (2020) which found that competence has a positive and significant effect on work stress. Research conducted by Satriani and Sukma (2024), Setiadi and Irawati (2023), Jina Kim and Hye-Sun Jung (2022), Pradnyani and Rahyuda (2022), Pramesthi, et al., (2020) found that competence has a negative and significant effect on work stress.

H2: Competence has a negative and significant effect on Work Stress of Employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province.

The Role of Workload as a Mediator

According to Manullang (2021), organizational culture has a significant influence on employee workload. A negative organizational culture can lead to excessive workload. Conversely, a positive organizational culture can make a big difference in terms of employee workload. A positive organizational culture can increase employee motivation, engagement, and productivity. According to Robins & Judge (2017), many professionals view the pressure of heavy workloads and deadlines as positive challenges that drive the quality of their work and the satisfaction they get from their work. However, when the situation becomes negative, stress becomes dangerous and will hinder employee progress. Task demands that cause excessive workload are considered to increase anxiety and stress in employees.

H3: There is a positive and significant influence of Organizational Culture on Work Stress mediated by the Workload of Employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province.

Kuchinke & Johnson (2020) stated that employees with high competence are able to handle more complex tasks and responsibilities, so that they have the knowledge and skills needed to complete the work efficiently and effectively. Therefore, employees can be given heavier responsibilities and higher workloads than employees with lower competence. Tarwaka (2011) stated that excessive workload can increase tension in a person, causing stress. This is caused by excessive skill demands, excessive work speed, excessive work volume, and excessive working hours.

H4: There is a positive and significant influence of Competence on Work Stress mediated by the Workload of Employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework
Source: Based on theory and journal

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative research design that aims to determine the effect of Organizational Culture and Competence on Job Stress, with Workload as a mediating variable. The study was conducted at the Office of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. In ensuring the validity and reliability of the results, a structured survey was conducted on employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province and the data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with SmartPLS 4.1.0 software.

Research Design and Approach

A quantitative research design was chosen for this study because it can allow for the collection of measurable data, so that the data can be analyzed statistically to test the research hypothesis and assess and analyze the relationship between variables. The use of survey instruments can provide a standard way to collect data from a large group of respondents, allowing this study to determine and examine the impact of Organizational Culture, Competence, and Workload on Employee Job Stress.

Quantitative research method is a scientific method whose data is in the form of numbers or figures that can be processed and analyzed using mathematical or statistical calculations (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017). In this study, the focus is on understanding the direct and indirect effects of Organizational Culture and Competence on Job Stress, with Workload acting as a potential mediator. The reason for choosing SEM as an analysis method in this study is because SEM has the ability to assess several relationships simultaneously, both direct effects and indirect effects or mediation, and can also assess the interaction between latent constructs. Therefore, the selection or use of SEM is very appropriate because it can create a complexity of the research model.

Sampling Method

The sampling method in this study used saturated sampling (census) where the entire population was sampled, namely 71 employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. The reason the researcher chose to use the saturated sampling technique is, according to Arikunto (2012) if the population is less than 100 people, then the total number of

samples is taken, but if the population is greater than 100 people, then 10-15% or 20-25% of the population can be taken. Based on this study, because the population is not greater than 100 respondents, the researcher took 100% of the population at the General Election Commission Office of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, namely 71 employees. Thus, because the entire population was sampled, it is called a saturated sampling technique (census).

Classification of Research Variables

Research variables are anything that can differentiate or change values. Values can differ at different times for the same object or person, or at the same time for different objects or people (Sekaran and Bougie, 2017). In this study, there are three variables, namely the dependent variable, the independent variable, and the mediating variable. In this study, Organizational Culture (X1) and Competence (X2) are independent variables, while Workload acts as a mediating variable (Z) and Job Stress is the dependent variable (Y).

The dependent variable is the variable that is the main concern of the researcher (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017). The dependent variable in this study is Work Stress (Y). The independent variable is the variable that influences the dependent variable, either positively or negatively (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017). The independent variables in this study are Organizational Culture (X1) and Competence (X2). The mediating variable is the variable that appears between when the independent variable begins to influence the dependent variable, and when the influence of the independent variable is felt on the dependent variable (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017). The mediating variable in this study is Workload (Z).

Survey Instrument

Data collection techniques in this study were carried out using observation, interview, and questionnaire methods. The role of the researcher when collecting observation data was as a non-participant. In non-participant observation, the researcher is never directly involved in the actions of the actors, but observes them from outside the actor's visual range, for example through one-way glass or a camera (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017). In this study, the researcher used an unstructured interview type. It is called unstructured because the interviewer does not enter the interview situation with a series of planned questions that will be given to the respondents (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017). The type of question in the questionnaire in this study is a closed question. Closed questions ask respondents to make choices between a series of alternatives provided by the researcher (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017). The questionnaire in this study contains statements related to the variables in this study, namely the Organizational Culture variable, Competence variable, Workload variable, and Work Stress variable. In this research questionnaire, the researcher provides answer choices that will later be selected by the respondents. To obtain the data, questionnaires were distributed to respondents, namely employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. In short, the survey instrument used in this study consisted of multiple-choice questions or closed questions, Likert scale items, and several open-ended questions asked during interviews to gather quantitative and qualitative insights.

The survey items used for each variable are taken from the theories of leading experts that are in accordance with the phenomena, conditions, and problems that occur in the research object in this study, namely at the Office of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. For Organizational Culture, items related to the regularity of observed behavior, norms, dominant values, philosophy, rules, and organizational climate are taken from the theory according to Luthans (2011). The Competency Scale includes items related to knowledge, understanding, abilities, values, attitudes, and interests taken from the theory according to Gordon (2017). For Workload, items related to work conditions, use of working time, and targets to be achieved are taken from the theory according to Koesmowidjojo (2017). Meanwhile, Job Stress is measured using items related to the consequences of work stress consisting of physiological, psychological, and behavioral symptoms taken from the theory according to Robbins & Judge (2017).

For each item in the survey, it is assessed on a 5-point Likert scale, starting from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). This scale was chosen because of its simplicity and its ability to measure the intensity of respondents' attitudes or perceptions of certain statements (Cohen et al., 2017). A total of 49 questions were included in the final survey, which were filled out by respondents by giving them the freedom not to include their name identity (anonymous). The researcher determined this in order to encourage respondents to provide honest responses.

Data Collection Process

Data collection took one week. Employees at the Office of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province were invited to participate in filling out a printed and distributed survey. To provide detailed clarity to the participants, several explanations were given, such as the purpose of the study, how to fill out the survey, and the guarantee of confidentiality of identity so that participants could provide truly honest feedback. The survey was distributed to 71 employees, and all employees were willing to provide responses, resulting in a response rate of 100%. The responses from the employees were then inputted into a laptop for management and analysis. This sample size was considered sufficient for SEM, ensuring that the results were statistically significant and robust.

Data Analysis

This study consists of descriptive analysis and quantitative analysis. Descriptive analysis is carried out with the aim of being able to explain the characteristics of respondents (such as age, gender, last education, work section or division, and length of service). In addition, descriptive analysis in this study will also explain the characteristics of respondents regarding the variables in this study. Furthermore, quantitative analysis, the data analysis method used in this study is Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) using SmartPLS 4.1.0 software. After all the data was collected, the data was analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to assess the direct and indirect relationships between variables. SEM is a statistical technique that combines factor analysis and multiple regression analysis to evaluate complex models involving many variables and constructs (Hair et al., 2010).

SEM is very appropriate for this study because using SEM allows for the examination of the direct effects of Organizational Culture and Competence on Job Stress, as well as the indirect effects through Workload as a mediator. The measurement model is then assessed to evaluate the validity and reliability of all survey items. This process includes checking convergent validity (using outer loading criteria), discriminant validity (for example, using cross loading criteria), AVE, and composite reliability, as well as Cronbach's alpha. Then after the measurement model is validated, testing is carried out on the structural model to assess the relationship between Organizational Culture, Competence, Workload, and Job Stress. The structural model is evaluated with the R square value for each dependent latent variable as the predictive power of the structural model, Q square as predictive relevance (the principle is the same as R square as goodness of fit), parameter coefficients, and P values. Hypothesis testing by looking at the original sample estimate value, standard error, and comparing the t-statistic value with the t-table (Ghozali and Latan, 2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study provide a detailed understanding of the relationship between Organizational Culture, Competence, Workload, and Job Stress in the context of the Yogyakarta Special Region Provincial Election Commission Office. The main objective of this study was to examine and analyze the direct and indirect effects of Organizational Culture and Competence on Job Stress, with Workload as a potential mediating variable. Data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), which allows a thorough investigation of the direct and indirect (mediation) relationships between the main constructs in the research model.

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis of Respondents

Before delving into the hypothesis testing, descriptive statistics of all survey responses were examined. The sample consisted of 71 valid responses from employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. This survey was designed to be able to describe or depict the characteristics of respondents including: age, gender, last education, work section or division, and length of service based on respondents' answers to the research questionnaire, as well as the perceptions of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province regarding the impact of Organizational Culture, Competence, and Workload on Job Stress. The results of the descriptive analysis of respondents are shown in Table 1 Respondent Characteristics.

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

<i>Respondent Identity</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>		<i>Percentage</i>		
Gender	Male	Female	39	32	55%	45%
	Total		71		100%	
Age	22-28 Years	29-	18		25%	
	35 Years	36-42	11	19	15%	
	Years	43-49	17	4	27%	
	Years	50-56	2	71	24%	6%
	Years	57-63			3%	
	Years	Total			100%	
Last Education	Senior High School	Diploma	19	4	27%	
	Bachelor	Masters	34	14	6%	
	Total		71		48%	
					20%	100%
Year of Service	1-6 Years	7-	28	9	39%	13%
	12 Years	13-	29	2	41%	
	19 Years	20-	3	71	3%	4%
	26 Years	27-			100%	
	33 Years	Total				
Work Division	Commissioner	Secretary	5	1	7%	1%
	Finance, General, and Logistics	Planning,	37	18	52%	
	Data, and Technical	Information	10		25%	
	Election Organizers, Participation, and Public		71		14%	
	Relations, Law, and Human Resources	Total			100%	

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that the majority of employees working at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province are dominated by employees aged 36-42 years (27%), this is because in the past, in recruiting employees by recruiting regional employees with the main criteria of employees who already have a long work period and work experience. So that the majority of employees are dominated by employees aged 36-42 years. In terms of gender, the number of male and female employees tends to be balanced, this is because the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province does not apply rules related to gender in recruiting employees, thus providing equal opportunities for both men and women. From the last education, the majority of employees working at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province are dominated by employees with a bachelor's degree, this is because almost all of the job vacancies at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province have a bachelor's degree as their last education requirement. In terms of length of service, it is dominated by employees who have worked for 13-19 years. This is because the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province has a system of providing work contracts until retirement for employees and is also very open about promotions for employees who have good work achievements. So that the majority of employees who work at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province have a fairly long work period, which is around 13-19 years. Finally, when viewed from the work section, it is dominated by employees in the Finance, General, and Logistics sections. This is because the Finance, General, and Logistics Sections are work divisions that can be said to have quite important tasks and require extra care.

Table 2. Descriptive Analysis of Variables

<i>Variable</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Organizational Culture (X1)	71	2.00	5.00	4.18
Competence (X2)	71	2.65	5.00	4.22
Workload (Z)	71	3.00	5.00	4.36
Work Stress (Y)	71	2.00	5.00	3.96

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on Table 2, it is known that the average value for Organizational Culture is relatively high, which indicates that the agency and all employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta feel that they already have and display a strong organizational culture based on indicators of organizational culture which include behavioral regularity, norms, dominant values, philosophy, rules, and organizational climate. The aspects of Organizational Culture that received the highest scores include norms and rules, which indicate that all employees have become accustomed to doing work according to their respective duties with behavior in accordance with standard norms and the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta has instilled improvements in the quality of employee work from time to time. Likewise, Competence is rated very high, especially in areas related to values and interests. This shows that employees are always honest in many ways and have a high personal interest in always trying to develop their abilities. Then, the role of Workload as a mediator in influencing the Work Stress of employees gets positive results. All employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province without exception must submit to and obey the regulations issued by the KPU RI, but there is a condition that the central party in issuing regulations is very slow, so that when the regulations are issued it is close to the deadline for the implementation of the General Election stages. This makes it difficult for most employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province to overcome and organize the existing workload, because they have to immediately study, adjust and adopt the regulations to carry out the stages of the General Election, with a very limited time deadline resulting in high work conditions, excessive use of time, and high targets to be achieved. The existence of a heavy workload ultimately causes work stress felt by employees. Each employee at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province can handle two to three sub-sections of work at once, so employees who have high competence can have responsibility for important tasks not only in one sub-section but also in other sub-sections. This happens because, there is a tendency in the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province that the high competence possessed by employees allows the employees to be given and able to complete many important or difficult task responsibilities. The many important tasks that are the responsibility cause a big difference in the employee's workload because it will affect the high work conditions, excessive use of working hours, and high targets that must be achieved, with this condition causing work stress felt by employees.

Measurement Model Evaluation

Before assessing the structural relationships, the measurement model was evaluated for validity and reliability. The outer model was evaluated through convergent validity, discriminant validity (cross loading), AVE (Average Variance Extracted), and composite reliability strengthened by the cronbach's alpha value.

Convergent validity is declared high if it correlates more than 0.70 with the measured construct. The outer loading value used in this study is > 0.70. Discriminant validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators is assessed based on the cross loading value of the measurement with the construct. If the correlation of the construct with the measurement item is greater than the size of the other constructs, then this indicates that the latent construct can predict the size of the block better than the size of the other blocks. Then, the AVE value must be greater than 0.50. In measuring the reliability of a construct, there are 2 (two) ways, namely, the composite reliability value and the Cronbach's alpha value which has a criterion of > 0.70 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

Table 3. Outer Loading

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Outer Loading</i>	<i>Description</i>	
Organizational Culture (X1)	X1.1.1	0.862	Valid	Valid
	X1.1.2	0.906	Valid	Valid
	X1.2.1	0.839	Valid	Valid
	X1.2.2	0.739	Valid	Valid
	X1.3.1	0.913	Valid	Valid
	X1.3.2	0.847	Valid	
	X1.4.1	0.863		
	X1.5.1	0.890		
	X1.5.2	0.827		
	X1.6.1	0.776		
	X1.6.2	0.889		
	Competence (X2)	X2.1.1	0.871	Valid
X2.1.2		0.900	Valid	Valid
X2.1.3		0.793	Valid	Valid
X2.2.1		0.845	Valid	Valid
X2.2.2		0.900	Valid	Valid
X2.3.1		0.851	Valid	
X2.3.2		0.895	Valid	Valid
X2.3.3		0.871	Valid	Valid
X2.4.1		0.760	Valid	Valid
X2.4.2		0.900		
X2.4.3		0.767		
X2.5.1		0.712		
X2.5.2		0.718		
X2.5.3		0.830		
X2.6.1		0.797		
X2.6.2	0.733			
X2.6.3	0.784			
Workload (Z)	Z.1.1	0.838	Valid	Valid
	Z.1.2	0.757	Valid	Valid
	Z.1.3	0.870	Valid	
	Z.2.1	0.834	Valid	Valid
	Z.2.2	0.812	Valid	Valid
	Z.2.3	0.860		
	Z.3.1	0.797		
	Z.3.2	0.702		
	Z.3.3	0.743		
Work Stress (Y)	Y.1.1	0.769	Valid	Valid
	Y.1.2	0.906	Valid	Valid
	Y.1.3	0.772	Valid	
	Y.2.1	0.887	Valid	Valid
	Y.2.2	0.769	Valid	Valid
	Y.2.3	0.906		

	Y.2.4	0.879	Valid	Valid
	Y.2.5	0.796	Valid	
	Y.2.6	0.742		
	Y.3.1	0.713		
	Y.3.2	0.742		
	Y.3.3	0.841		

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on Table 3, it is known that each indicator of the research variable has an outer loading > 0.70. This shows that the outer loading of the variables Organizational Culture, Competence, Workload, and Work Stress are valid and reliable because they have met the requirements of convergent validity.

Table 4. Cross Loading

Variable	Workload	Organizational Culture	Competence	Work Stress			
X1.1.1	0.344	0.862	0.906	0.386	0.507	0.443	
X1.1.2	0.344	0.839	0.739	0.350		0.336	
X1.2.1	0.272	0.913	0.847	0.167		0.450	
X1.2.2	0.253	0.863	0.890	0.270		0.538	
X1.3.1	0.422	0.827	0.776	0.299		0.405	
X1.3.2	0.262	0.889		0.304		0.539	
X1.4.1	0.354			0.350		0.547	
X1.5.1	0.389			0.395		0.355	
X1.5.2	0.307			0.245		0.357	
X1.6.1	0.192			0.314		0.371	
X1.6.2	0.290			0.164			
X2.1.1	0.370	0.222	0.247	0.871		0.361	
X2.1.2	0.343	0.393	0.312	0.900		0.393	
X2.1.3	0.471	0.247	0.206	0.793		0.378	
X2.2.1	0.247	0.308	0.173	0.845		0.322	
X2.2.2	0.343	0.334	0.247	0.900		0.393	
X2.3.1	0.379	0.383	0.350	0.851		0.336	
X2.3.2	0.303	0.356	0.328	0.895		0.371	
X2.3.3	0.355	0.345	0.218	0.871		0.403	
X2.4.1	0.403	0.294		0.760		0.305	
X2.4.2	0.343			0.900		0.393	
X2.4.3	0.417			0.767		0.303	
X2.5.1	0.248			0.712		0.376	
X2.5.2	0.315			0.718		0.349	
X2.5.3	0.220			0.830		0.282	
X2.6.1	0.304			0.797		0.278	
X2.6.2	0.126			0.733		0.201	
X2.6.3	0.306			0.784		0.284	
Z.1.1	0.838	0.449	0.332	0.249		0.502	
Z.1.2	0.757	0.354	0.274	0.306		0.332	0.502
Z.1.3	0.870	0.284	0.340	0.446		0.500	

Z.2.1	0.834	0.268	0.110	0.397	0.448
Z.2.2	0.812	0.237		0.356	0.440
Z.2.3	0.860			0.405	0.436
Z.3.1	0.797			0.151	0.334
Z.3.2	0.702			0.210	0.514
Z.3.3	0.743			0.347	
Y.1.1	0.417	0.321	0.520	0.240	0.769
Y.1.2	0.579	0.318		0.368	0.906
Y.1.3	0.352	0.470		0.336	0.772
Y.2.1	0.493	0.477		0.368	0.887
Y.2.2	0.342	0.513		0.326	0.769
Y.2.3	0.568	0.457	0.418	0.364	0.906
Y.2.4	0.481	0.281	0.570	0.370	0.879
Y.2.5	0.521	0.282		0.272	0.796
Y.2.6	0.260	0.397		0.368	0.742
Y.3.1	0.398			0.489	0.713
Y.3.2	0.307			0.306	0.742
Y.3.3	0.601			0.259	0.841

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on Table 4, the indicators of the Organizational Culture, Competence, Workload, and Work Stress variables after the cross loading or discriminant validity test are valid, because the cross loading value is > 0.50 and is greater than the other cross loading values.

Table 5. AVE (Average Variance Extracted)

Variable	AVE	Criteria	Description
Organizational Culture (X1)	0.725	> 0.50	Valid
Competence (X2)	0.675	> 0.50	Valid
Workload (Z)	0.645	> 0.50	Valid
Work Stress (Y)	0.661	> 0.50	Valid

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on Table 5, All variables have AVE values > 0.50. Thus, it can be stated that the variables of Organizational Culture, Competence, Workload, and Job Stress have good validity.

Table 6. Composite Reliability

Variable	Composite Reliability	Criteria	Description
Organizational Culture (X1)	0.971	> 0.70	Valid
Competence (X2)	0.973	> 0.70	Valid
Workload (Z)	0.939	> 0.70	Valid
Work Stress (Y)	0.961	> 0.70	Valid

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on Table 6, each variable has a Composite Reliability value > 0.70. Thus, it can be stated that the variables Organizational Culture, Competence, Workload, and Job Stress have high reliability values.

Table 7. Cronbach's Alpha

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Description</i>
Organizational Culture (X1)	0.962	> 0.70	Valid
Competence (X2)	0.970	> 0.70	Valid
Workload (Z)	0.931	> 0.70	Valid
Work Stress (Y)	0.953	> 0.70	Valid

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on Table 7, each variable also has a Cronbach's Alpha value > 0.70. Thus, it can be stated that the variables of Organizational Culture, Competence, Workload, and Job Stress have high reliability values.

Structural Model Evaluation

The next step is related to the assessment of the structural model, which analyzes the relationship between constructs. In SEM, the structural model will evaluate the direct and indirect relationships (mediation) between variables and provide insight into the strength and direction of the relationship. The structural model is evaluated with the R square value for each dependent latent variable as the predictive strength of the structural model, Q square as predictive relevance (the principle is the same as R square as goodness of fit), parameter coefficients, and P values. Hypothesis testing by looking at the original sample estimate value, standard error, and comparing the t-statistic value with the t-table (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). From the results of the structural model analysis, several main findings emerged.

Table 8. R-Square

<i>Variable</i>	<i>R-Square</i>	<i>Adjusted R-Square</i>
Workload (Z)	0.228	0.205
Work Stress (Y)	0.452	0.427

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Table 9. Hypothesis Test Results

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Original sample (O)</i>	<i>Sample mean (M)</i>	<i>Standard deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>T statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P values</i>
Organizational Culture (X1) → Work Stress (Y)	0.338	0.338	0.106	3.183	0.001
Competence (X2) → Work Stress (Y)	0.145	0.148	0.070	2.069	0.019
Organizational Culture (X1) → Workload (Z) → Work Stress (Y)	0.100	0.107	0.043	2.300	0.011
Competence (X2) → Workload (Z) → Work Stress (Y)	0.118	0.121	0.044	2.673	0.004

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Figure 2. Bootstrapping Test
 Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Hypothesis Testing 1

The analysis revealed that Organizational Culture and Competence have a positive and significant impact on Job Stress. In more detail, the influence of Organizational Culture on Job Stress obtained an original sample value of 0.338. A positive original sample value indicates that the direction of the relationship is positive. Then the t-count value of 3.183 > from the t-table and the p-value of 0.001 < from the critical value of 0.05 indicates that organizational culture has a significant effect on the work stress of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. Hypothesis 1 is supported or accepted.

Hypothesis Testing 2

Similarly, Competence has a positive and significant influence on Job Stress, obtained an original sample value of 0.145. A positive original sample value indicates that the direction of the relationship is positive. Then the t-value of 2.069 > t-table and the p-value of 0.019 < from the critical value of 0.05 indicates that competence has a significant effect on the work stress of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. Hypothesis 2 is rejected.

Hypothesis Testing 3

The main focus of this study is to test and analyze whether Workload mediates the relationship between Organizational Culture, Competence, and Job Stress. The results show that, for the mediation of Workload between Organizational Culture and Job Stress,

the original sample value is 0.100. A positive original sample value indicates that the direction of the relationship is positive. Then the t-count value of 2,300 > t-table and the p-value of 0.011 < from the critical value of 0.05 indicate that workload significantly mediates the influence of organizational culture on the work stress of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. Hypothesis 3 is supported or accepted.

Hypothesis Testing 4

Similarly, for the mediation of Workload between Competence and Job Stress, the original sample value is 0.118. A positive original sample value indicates that the direction of the relationship is positive. Then the t-count value of 2.673 > t-table and p-values of 0.004 < critical value of 0.05 indicate that workload significantly mediates the effect of competence on work stress of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. Hypothesis 3 is supported or accepted.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study provide important insights and knowledge regarding the relationship between Organizational Culture, Competence, Workload, and Job Stress of employees at the Office of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. Specifically, the results of this study explain and confirm that Organizational Culture and Competence independently contribute to increased Job Stress. In addition, this study also explains and confirms that the integration of Workload as a mediator between Organizational Culture, Competence, and Job Stress is positive and statistically significant. This section will review these findings in more depth and detail.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Work Stress

The results of this study indicate that Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Job Stress of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. Based on the results of the data processing that has been carried out, the value of the original sample was obtained at 0.338 with a p-value of 0.001 and a t-value of 3.183. This means that when the Organizational Culture in the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province is oriented towards the regularity of observed behavior, strong norms, dominant values, philosophy, rules, and organizational climate, it will affect the increasing work stress, which is in the form of the emergence of physiological symptoms, psychological symptoms, and behavioral symptoms that increase. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by Edwin (2023), Clarisa, et al., (2022), and Komar (2021) which found that Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on Job Stress. Meanwhile, research conducted by Aulia (2021) and Sofiana, et al., (2021) showed that Organizational Culture has no effect on Job Stress.

The Influence of Competence on Work Stress

The results of this study indicate that competence has a positive and significant effect on work stress of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. Based on the results of the calculations that have been carried out, the value of the original sample is 0.145 with a p-value of 0.019 and a t-value of 2.069. This means that when the Competence possessed by employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province is oriented towards high knowledge, understanding, abilities, values, attitudes, and interests, but is not in accordance with the competencies needed to carry out the work that is their responsibility, it will affect the increasing work stress, which is in the form of the emergence of physiological symptoms, psychological symptoms, and behavioral symptoms that increase. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by Maliki, et al., (2024) showing that Competence has a positive and significant effect on Work Stress. Meanwhile, research conducted by Tunga, et al., (2023), Lestari and Darmo (2022) shows that Competence has no effect on Work Stress.

Workload Mediates the Influence of Organizational Culture on Work Stress

The results of the study indicate that workload mediates the influence of organizational culture on work stress of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. Based on the results of the calculations that have been carried out, the value of the original sample is 0.100 with a p-value of 0.011 and a t-value of 2.300. This means that when the organizational culture in the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province is oriented towards the regularity of observed behavior, strong norms, dominant values, philosophy, rules, and organizational climate, it will affect the workload felt by employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province who are oriented

towards high work conditions, excessive use of time, and high targets to be achieved, with this condition causing work stress felt by employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province in the form of physiological symptoms, psychological symptoms, and behavioral symptoms to increase.

According to Manullang (2021), organizational culture has a significant influence on employee workload. A negative organizational culture can lead to excessive workload. Conversely, a positive organizational culture can make a big difference in terms of employee workload. A positive organizational culture can increase employee motivation, engagement, and productivity. This is supported by research conducted by Adha, et al., (2024) and Clarisa, et al., (2022) which found that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on workload. According to Robins & Judge (2017), many professionals view the pressure of heavy workloads and deadlines as positive challenges that drive the quality of their work and the satisfaction they get from their work. However, when the situation becomes negative, stress becomes dangerous and will hinder employee progress. Task demands that cause excessive workloads are considered to increase anxiety and stress in employees. This is supported by research conducted by Maliki, et al., (2024), Putra, et al., (2024), Yuanto and Anwar (2024), Suspahariati, et al., (2023), Priandari and Adnyani (2023), Caniago and Pravitasmara (2023), Cahaya and Hermina (2023), Wirawan (2022), Lestari and Darmo (2022), Fatika K.M. (2022), M.K. Raharja and K.K. Heryanda (2021), Budhiartini (2021), Ananda, et al., (2021), Pramesthi, et al., (2020), Marbella (2020), Maulina and Lukito (2020) found that workload has a positive and significant effect on work stress. Meanwhile, research conducted by Ardiyanti (2024), Tungka, et al., (2023), Amalia (2023), and Aulia (2022) showed that workload had no effect on work stress. Likewise, research conducted by Clarisa, et al., (2022) showed that workload could not mediate the influence of organizational culture on work stress.

Based on the opinions of experts and the results of previous studies, it can be concluded that workload as a mediating variable for work stress felt by employees of the Yogyakarta Special Region Provincial Election Commission is caused by the existing organizational culture. All employees of the Yogyakarta Special Region Provincial Election Commission without exception must submit to and obey the regulations issued by the center, but there is a condition that the center takes a long time to issue regulations, so that when the regulations are issued, it is close to the deadline for the General Election implementation stages. This makes it difficult for employees of the Yogyakarta Special Region Provincial Election Commission to overcome and organize the existing workload, because they must immediately study, adjust and adopt the regulations to carry out the stages of the Election, with a very limited time deadline, resulting in high work conditions, excessive use of time, and high targets to be achieved. The existence of a heavy workload ultimately causes work stress felt by employees of the Yogyakarta Special Region Provincial Election Commission in the form of the emergence of physiological symptoms, psychological symptoms and behavioral symptoms to increase.

Workload Mediates the Influence of Competence on Work Stress

The results of the study indicate that workload mediates the effect of competence on work stress of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. Based on the results of the calculations that have been carried out, the value of the original sample is 0.118 with a p-value of 0.004 and a t-value of 2.673. This means that when the competence possessed by employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province is oriented towards high knowledge, understanding, ability, values, attitudes, and interests, it will affect the workload felt by employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province who are oriented towards high work conditions, excessive use of time, and high targets to be achieved, with this condition causing work stress felt by employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province in the form of the emergence of physiological symptoms, psychological symptoms, and behavioral symptoms to increase.

Kuchinke & Johnson (2020) stated that employees who have high competence are able to handle more complex tasks and responsibilities, so that they have the knowledge and skills needed to complete work efficiently and effectively. Therefore, employees can be given heavier responsibilities and higher workloads than employees with lower competence. This is supported by research conducted by Femy Noviantari (2023) which found that competence has a positive and significant effect on workload. Tarwaka (2011) stated that too much workload can increase tension in a person, causing stress. This is caused by excessive skill demands, excessive work speed, excessive work volume, and too long working hours. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by Maliki, et al., (2024), Putra, et al., (2024), Yuanto and Anwar (2024), Suspahariati, et al., (2023), Priandari and Adnyani (2023), Caniago and Pravitasmara (2023), Cahaya and Hermina (2023), Wirawan (2022), Lestari and Darmo (2022), Fatika K.M. (2022), M.K. Raharja and K.K. Heryanda (2021), Budhiartini (2021), Ananda, et al., (2021), Pramesthi, et al., (2020),

Marbella (2020), Maulina and Lukito (2020) found that workload has a positive and significant effect on work stress. Meanwhile, research conducted by Ardiyanti (2024), Tungka, et al., (2023), Amalia (2023), and Aulia (2022) showed that workload had no effect on work stress.

Based on the opinions of experts and the results of previous studies, it can be concluded that workload as a mediating variable for work stress felt by employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province is caused by the high competence possessed by employees. In the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, there is a tendency that employees who have high competence are always trusted to handle important tasks. This condition is exacerbated by the fact that each employee at the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province can handle two to three sub-sections of work at once, so employees who have high competence can have responsibility for important tasks not only in one sub-section but also in other sub-sections. The large number of important tasks that are the responsibility causes a big difference in employee workload because it will affect high work conditions, excessive use of working hours, and high targets that must be achieved, with this condition causing work stress felt by employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province in the form of physiological symptoms, psychological symptoms, and behavioral symptoms to increase.

CONCLUSION

This study aims to test and analyze the influence of Organizational Culture and Competence on Work Stress directly and indirectly through Workload as a Mediator with a focus on employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province. Based on the results of the data analysis that has been carried out, the results of the study obtained that Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on work stress of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, Competence has a positive and significant effect on work stress of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, Workload mediates positively and significantly the effect of organizational culture on work stress of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, and finally Workload mediates positively and significantly the effect of competence on work stress of employees of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province.

Limitations

This study did not consider several other external variables that may have an influence on employee Job Stress, such as personal factors (e.g., job satisfaction, organizational commitment, motivation) and organizational factors (e.g., work environment, leadership style). Further researchers are expected to include these variables in the research to be conducted, so that they can find out and analyze more completely the variables that influence Job Stress. In addition, the limited sample at the Office of the General Election Commission of the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province also limits the generalization of the findings to be applied to a broader context.

Practical and Theoretical Implications

Based on the research conducted, the results of the study can provide contributions in the form of practical and theoretical implications. First, the practical implication is to control work stress felt by employees, the DIY Provincial KPU should create a more positive organizational culture, ensure that each employee has high competence that is appropriate or suitable for the field of work that is their responsibility, and carry out careful management of the existing workload, handling work stress based on these factors can help control work stress felt by employees as a whole, encouraging the DIY Provincial KPU to always coordinate periodically with the Indonesian KPU to ensure clarity regarding existing regulations or guidelines for assignments, starting from the time of delegation, details of the contents of the assignment, and the deadline for completion.

Second, the results of this study have broad theoretical implications and can be applied to explore more deeply the variables of organizational culture, competence, workload, and work stress, analyze how the variables of organizational culture, competence, and workload influence work stress, analyze how the role of workload mediates the influence of organizational culture and competence variables on work stress, and identify that there are still other variables that can influence work stress, so that further studies can be carried out for subsequent researchers to further explore and analyze the influence of other variables on work stress.

Future Research Directions

Future research should focus on a more in-depth analysis of the role of Workload as a mediator between Organizational Culture, Competence, and Job Stress. This needs to be done in order to further enrich studies and literature that test and analyze the role of Workload as a mediator between Organizational Culture, Competence, and Job Stress, which currently there are still few researchers who have conducted tests and analyses related to this. However, the limitations of research and literature on the role of Workload as a mediator between Organizational Culture, Competence, and Job Stress can be an opportunity for new research.

Furthermore, further research can investigate in more depth one of the findings that is quite different from most previous studies, namely the positive and significant influence of competence on work stress. Is the positive and significant influence of competence on work stress only caused by the existence of a mismatch between work and the competence possessed and the amount of work that is the responsibility or are there other factors that also allow for a positive and significant influence of competence on work stress.

In conclusion, the findings of this study show the importance of managing and creating a positive Organizational Culture and giving employees job responsibilities according to their field of Competence and managing them appropriately and in a balanced manner regarding the amount of work that is the responsibility of each employee, so that the workload felt by employees will feel lighter and ultimately will make the work stress felt by employees can always be controlled.

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